

Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 2B

Analysis libraries or domain libraries (e.g. SolarSoft, XSPEC, Sunpy,
Astropy)

Code associated with research (e.g. for publications)

General analysis software for wide use (e.g. SciPy)

Fostering better collaboration in software development cycles between scientists and programmers to ensure the integrity of and promote the development of new scientific data products

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- Abstract 2B-1

bitly

CERES/TISA Product Team etc. → (Climate Quality Data Record of Observed TOA Fluxes)

Python-based Package to Combine and Analyze Spaceborne and Ground- based Precipitation Datasets

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<https://qr.link/HesC0B>

1. Earth Precipitation Instrumentation

Rain gauge/Disdrometer
(Point)

Gauge/Disdrometer
(Network)
 $\Delta x 0.1$ to 10 km

Precipitation Radar
(Volume $0.01 - 1$ km³
Coverage up to 1000 km²)

Precipitation Satellite
($\Delta x 5$ to 50 km,
Swath $10^2 - 10^4$ km)

How do we compare?

Use SIMBA!

2. System for Integrating Multiplatform Data to Build the Atmospheric Column

3. Applications

BatAnalysis: A Comprehensive Python Pipeline for Swift BAT Data Analysis

**Tyler Parsotan¹ & the Swift
Burst Alert Telescope Team**

1. NASA GSFC, Astroparticle Physics Lab
(661); tyler.parsotan@nasa.gov

Website: <https://github.com/parsotat/BatAnalysis>

Documentation/Tutorials:
<https://github.com/parsotat/BatAnalysis/tree/main/notebooks>

The Swift Burst Alert Telescope has 20 years of hard X-ray data that is difficult to process...

○ Unidentified ● Unknown AGN ● Seyfert Galaxies ● CVs/Stars ● X-ray Binaries
 ● LINER ● Galaxy Clusters ● Beamed AGN ● Pulsars/SNR

There are a total of 1632 sources identified in the 105 month survey where 422 are new detections

The BatAnalysis tool allows users to easily get to the astrophysical lightcurves and spectra that are needed. It allows for easy:

- querying/downloading of data,
- processing/calibration of data,
- creation of lightcurves & spectra at any time binning

E.g. Search for Transient MAXI J0637-430

Website

<https://www.astrochemistry.org/pahdb/>

GitHub

<https://github.com/PAHdb/AmesPAHdbPythonSuite>

<https://github.com/PAHdb/AmesPAHdbIDLSuite>

<https://github.com/PAHdb/pyPAHdb>

The NASA Ames pyPAHdb software tool and its application on JWST observations

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Vincent Esposito, Alessandra Ricca, Els Peeters

Decomposing the JWST ERS-PDRs4All MIRI-MRS Orion Bar Observations With NASA Ames pyPAHdb

The Orion Bar Composite NIRCam Image (Chown et al. 2023)

pyPAHdb delivers the **PAH ionization (γ)** and **PAH size** maps from modeling of the 5-15 μm PAH emission spectrum

Obtaining the pure **PAH emission spectrum** from each of the $\sim 8,500$ pixels in the 9-tile MIRI-MRS mosaic, to be modeled with pyPAHdb

The recovered correlation between γ and the 6.2/11.2 PAH intensity ratio, a proxy for PAH ionization

Jet Propulsion Laboratory
California Institute of Technology

Where's Your README?

Helping Open Science Source Thrive Through Community-Developed Best Practices & Standards

Speaker: Rishi Verma

Affiliation: Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology

Contact: Rishi.Verma@jpl.nasa.gov

Website: <https://nasa-ammos.github.io/slim/>

Additional Slides: <https://tinyurl.com/slim-nasa-smd>

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Software Lifecycle Improvement & Modernization (SLIM)

"A community-resource for exchanging and implementing best practices in software lifecycle improvements."

<https://nasa-ammos.github.io/slim>

Our Scope

We focus on best practices related to **software project governance, documentation, and development life-cycles.**

Community Based

We solicit improvement ideas and solutions from **our community** deliver best practices back to our members.

Open Source

We treat best practices and **standards-as-code**. We iteratively improve our recommendations through the open source tickets and pull requests.

Our Impact

No. Best Practices

13

Specified

9

Developing

56

Backlogged

No. of Successfully Infused Best Practices

671

No. of Software Repositories Affected

211

A Python-based Radar Data Processing System for NASA's GPM Ground Validation Program

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GitHub

Poster

A Python-based Radar Data Processing System for NASA's GPM Ground Validation Program

NASA's Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) Ground Validation (GV) Program developed a Python-based radar processing system, GVRadar.

- Dual Polarimetric Quality Control (DPQC), which utilizes thresholds to remove non-precipitating radar echoes.
- Dual polarimetric precipitation product generation (dp_products) produces research quality precipitation products.

GVRadar will run with default settings, the recommended method is to use a user designated parameter dictionary.

- Dictionaries allow the user to control QC thresholds, specify fields to generate, select output options, and set plotting preferences.

GVRadar can retrieve model sounding data, allowing DPQC and dp_products to run in near real-time.

- Near real-time processing are available for NASA's Dual Polarimetric (NPOL) and Dual-frequency Dual-polarized Doppler Radar (D3R) radars.

Daily operational processing of 90 ground-based weather radars are performed by the GVRadar.

Developed as a user-friendly open-source radar processing tool that can be utilized freely by the scientific community.

- Code available on GitHub.
- What methods are available to promote GVRadar to the public and scientific community?

GES DISC Collaborations with Open-Source Communities to Migrate Data Collections to Cloud-Friendly ...

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Christine Smit^{1,3}, Mahabal Hegde¹

¹NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, ²Adnet Systems, ³Telophase

Software for the NASA Science Mission Directorate Workshop
NASA HQ – May 7-9, 2024

tinyurl.com/gesdisc-slides
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A cloud-friendly file storage format for chunked, compressed, N-dimensional arrays based on an open-source specification.

Desired selection Corresponding chunks

Our collaborations with open source software development and communities:

1. Leading the community development process for GeoZarr, an Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) specification to extend Zarr for storing geospatial observations.
2. Exploring solutions for managing and keeping up-to-date dynamic data. A potential solution is the generic lakeFS platform for git-like data version control.
3. Developing a Zarr extension for fast and cost-efficient data analysis by pre-computing and storing cumulative sums at the chunk level.

EXPLORE SCIENCE

Enabling Software Capabilities for Artemis Science Teams

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Software for the NASA Science Mission
Directorate Workshop
NASA HQ – May 7-9, 2024

National Aeronautics and
Space Administration

Full reference materials can
be found at:

<https://zenodo.org/records/11110397>

Enabling Artemis Science via Data and Software

- Deliberate integration of Artemis Science team within the broader human spaceflight flight team is underway
- Discovery of work needs of joint flight team is being pursued
- Creation of software capabilities that align with work needs to enable flight teams and science teams is in active development